

OpenMod Africa

A suite of linked and open-source models adapted to Africa

DELIVERABLE NO. 3.2

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List of Abbreviations

DER	Distributed Energy Resources
EAPP	Eastern Africa Power Pool
EV	Electric Vehicles
GENeSYS-MOD	The Global Energy System Model
IAMC	Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium
OM4A	Open Modelling toolbox For Africa
OS	Operating System
OSeMOSYS	Open-Source Energy Modelling System
WAPP	Western African Power Pool

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Executive Summary

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 – OpenMod4Africa (Open Modelling Toolbox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa) is a three-year project (2023–2026) about the development of an energy modelling toolbox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. Furthermore, capacity building in the use of models and further development of the toolbox, among African experts, is a core element in the project.

The main objective is to contribute to an improved and robust understanding of how to develop an energy and a power supply to all Africans by making available, demonstrating and using an open modelling Toolbox. The OM4A Toolbox is populated with a suite of open, integrated, state-of-the-art models and a common database including all necessary data for conducting, among others, scenario building exercises at regional and national level. Two case studies are being conducted to demonstrate the use of the Toolbox, and in addition provide new insights into important challenges related to the energy transition. The research in the project is done in dialogue with two stakeholder groups, one in the Eastern African Power Pool (EAPP) region and one in the Western African Power Pool (WAPP) region.

This deliverable (D3.2) is linked to the release of the Suite of linked and open-source models as part the OM4A Toolbox, developed in deliverable D4.2, now publicly available at <https://africanenergymodels.net/>. This accompanying report describes the toolbox and explains how users can access the suite of linked, open-source models tailored to the African context. Furthermore, we present and explain the implemented extensions of the models' functionalities as identified in D3.1.

The OM4A Toolbox includes the following six models:

- GENeSYS-MOD, which analyses long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transport;
- openTEPES, a decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and transmission expansion plan of a large-scale electric system;
- plan4res, a power system model, which includes a capacity expansion module (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections in a given year), focused on the optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and the simulation of the system operation. plan4res focuses on electricity;
- InfraFair, which determines the network utilisation by agents (demand and generators using the network) and countries and associated with this, the allocation of the cost of the network among agents or countries;
- OnSSET, a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas;
- EV-PV, whose goal is to support electric mobility planning, with a focus on predicting the spatio-temporal charging needs, the number of required charging stations, and the potential for PV energy to cover the charging demand. The model focuses on private passenger mobility. Within the framework of the project, a second model has been developed to also address public transport electrification.

In the previous deliverable 3.1, the functionalities of the current models were assessed concerning the openMod4Africa case studies' specifications. While no modifications to the mathematical modelling or solving algorithms are required for these models to address the relevant analyses at hand in the African context, GENeSYS-MOD, openTEPES, and plan4res needed some adaptations of the processing of input data to represent

specifically the deployment of certain technological solutions to address certain energy supply needs. These included improvements in demand-side modelling, particularly for cooking energy demand electrification, and enhancements in network modelling to account for the deployment of off-grid solutions to supply certain demand. As aforementioned, these have been implemented through data workflow updates. Furthermore, model updates included enhanced user support through additional documentation on model use. The installation and scripts were refactored to ensure compatibility with Linux environments, and the integrated workflow was tested by validating the data-processing linkages between GENeSYS-MOD, openTEPES, and plan4res.

InfraFair and OnSSET, already developed for the African context, required no model adaptations. The EV-PV module needed some extensions to include additional passenger transport modes (motorbikes, minibus taxis, regular buses, and rapid transit buses) and an adaptation of the PV potential assessment methodology to local conditions.

This report, for deliverable D3.2, builds upon deliverable 3.1, by discussing the actual development and implementation of the new model functionalities. This report also discusses those main issues encountered during the implementation process and shares lessons learned both during implementation and through interactions with African partners. Furthermore, the report explains how the suite of linked and open-source models adapted to Africa have been made available online to enable new users to easily access these models and use the openMod4Africa toolbox independently for their case studies.

1 Introduction

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 – OpenMod4Africa (Open Modelling Toolbox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa) is a three-year project (2023–2026) about development of an energy modelling toolbox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. Furthermore, capacity building among African experts in use and development of the toolbox is a core element in the project.

The main objective is to contribute to an improved and robust understanding of how to develop an energy and a power supply to all Africans by making available, demonstrating and using an open modelling Toolbox. The Toolbox will be populated with a suite of open integrated state-of-the-art models and a common database including all necessary data for conducting among other scenario building exercises at regional and national level. Two case studies are demonstrating the use of the Toolbox, and in addition providing new insight into important challenges related to the energy transition. The research in the project is done in dialogue with two stakeholder groups, one in the Eastern African Power Pool region and one in the Western African Power Pool region.

The overall objective of WP3, ‘Model development and adaptation’ is expanding the functionalities and adapting the features of the models within the Toolbox developed in WP4, so they can adequately represent the transition of energy systems in Africa towards secure, affordable, and clean energy for all. The specific objectives to be pursued related to the former are listed next:

1. Design and implementation of the integration of additional open-source models into the Toolbox.
2. Development of detailed specifications of the upgrades that the models should undergo.
3. Implementation of the upgrades to the models previously specified.

This deliverable, together with D3.3, completes Task 3.3: implementation of the upgrades to the models previously specified. Web access to the suite of models is available at <https://africaenergymodels.net/>. This document is the accompanying report, explains the changes to the models and provides a description of the toolbox and explaining how to access the suite of models and its documentation.

The main body of this document is composed of two chapters:

In chapter 2, we introduce the OM4A open energy system modelling toolbox, which includes the suite of linked and open-source models available to the public.

Chapter **Error! Reference source not found.** focuses on the process of development and implementation of new model functionalities as identified in D3.1, as well as additional updates beyond D3.1 that were identified during the work on this deliverable. For each extension, we specify whether it is model-related or IT-related, before delving into the corresponding upgrade. Model-related extensions refer to changes in the actual model formulation, such as improvements to equations or model logic, while IT-related extensions focus on aspects such as data processing, installation procedures, and user documentation. We then cover key aspects of it, including the rationale behind the change, the implementation approach, and its impact:

- The reason for the change is explained based on the partners’ needs, ensuring that each extension addresses specific functional or quality improvements.

- The implementation approach is outlined, detailing how the update was integrated and any challenges encountered during the process.
- We assess the effects of this upgrade on model use and discuss key learnings.

2 Accessing the suite of models: The OM4A Toolbox

This chapter introduces and explains the OM4A open energy system modelling toolbox, which can be accessed via <https://africanenergymodels.net>. The open energy modelling toolbox includes all models, installation guides, and user manuals. It also provides information on the case studies conducted within OM4A to test and validate the toolbox. Additionally, it features a database (the Scenario Explorer), which will later be populated with datasets related to the openMod4Africa case studies. A dedicated visualization tool is available to explore the results from the case studies. Finally, the toolbox includes a link to the Permanent Network site, which aims to foster the development of a community of African energy modelling experts and stakeholders, both within and beyond the OM4A Project.

The OM4A open energy system modelling toolbox on <https://africanenergymodels.net> is a comprehensive platform dedicated to advancing energy system modeling across the African continent. It is specifically designed to support researchers and practitioners in developing robust, data-driven energy strategies that are aligned with Africa's unique development priorities and sustainability goals.

This website facilitates the use of energy models that reflect the continent's diverse geographic, economic, and social contexts. By offering access to open-source tools, high-quality datasets, and opportunities for collaboration, [the toolbox](#) empowers its users to analyse and plan effective, sustainable energy transitions. The energy system modelling efforts conducted through the platform consider critical factors such as rapid population growth, energy access, security of supply, expanding economic activities, infrastructure development, and the urgent need to address climate change.

In doing so, the platform serves, not only as a technical resource hub, but also as a catalyst for building local capacity and fostering regional cooperation in the energy modelling community across Africa.

Its general structure is explained below:

Figure 1: OM4A Toolbox main menu

The main page when accessing <https://africanenergymodels.net> enables the users to navigate between multiple subpages (see Figure 1) that will be explained in the following:

■ Models

On the Models subpage, users are presented with an overview of all the models available in the OM4A Open Energy System Modelling Toolbox. Through provided links, users can access individual pages for each model, which offer more detailed information as well as links to the respective GitHub repositories where the models can be accessed to be installed and used. The GitHub repositories for each model follow a guideline

to ensure they are easy to use, informative, and consistent with the other repositories allowing a uniform and simplified experience for the user.

■ Data

The Data page provides users with detailed information on the standardized variable template and nomenclature package from the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC) used across the OM4A Toolbox. This IAMC format defines a consistent structure for variables, regions, and units used in energy system models, supporting transparency, interoperability, and collaboration across modelling teams.

■ Case Studies

The Case Studies page provides an overview of how the OM4A Toolbox is being used in real-world applications across Africa, featuring summaries that demonstrate its capacity to support energy planning and policy development. It serves as a practical reference for researchers and practitioners interested in how the toolbox is applied to address Africa's energy challenges.

On this page, users find detailed descriptions of the regional case studies in West Africa and East Africa, and Tunisia, including the objectives, leading institutions, geographic focus, and key themes considered. This page outlines the scope of each study and also highlights how the toolbox supports both technical insights and capacity building in local contexts.

■ Training

The Training subpage provides links for users to access training materials and the documentation for all the models available in the OM4A Toolbox, hosted under <https://github.com/OM4A-Training-Material>. This GitHub organization contains individual repositories for each model, offering a wide range of resources to support users in effectively working with the models. Furthermore, YouTube links are provided that enable the users to explore the main functionalities of the model (Installation, how to run the model etc.).

■ Visualisation

The Visualisation subpage offers an interactive way to explore the scenarios and case studies from the OM4A Toolbox. At the centre of the page is a map-based tool that allows users to visually engage with the geographic and model-based data.

Users can browse available case studies and scenarios directly on the map, gaining insights into how the OM4A models can be applied to different regions across the continent. For a more detailed and immersive experience, the page includes a button linking to the full version of the visualisation tool on its dedicated platform. This enables deeper exploration of data, model outputs, and regional energy system dynamics in an intuitive and user-friendly format.

■ Permanent Network

Links to the webpage of the African Energy Modelling Network (<https://africanenergymodellingnetwork.net/>), which highlights its core activities, including training, research support, and capacity building, and emphasizes its role in fostering innovation and providing evidence-based insights for policy and planning. It also presents the network's broader goal of enabling a just and sustainable energy transition by connecting academia, industry, and policymakers.

3 Implemented Model Extensions

This section outlines all the extensions implemented for each model. We firstly provide a brief introduction to the model and then cover the key aspects of model extensions, including the rationale behind the change, the implementation approach, and its impact on model use, as well as the extent to which it improves upon previous model versions, and how it was tested to ensure proper functionality.

The results will be presented in tables for each model, using colour coding to indicate whether the extensions are changes to the model itself or related to IT aspects, such as easier installation and use of the model. This approach allows users to better understand and utilize the models effectively. Each model section will begin with a short summary and an overview of the model extensions.

3.1 GENeSYS-MOD

The Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) is a linear open-source energy system model which is tailored to analyse long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transport. First published by Löffler et al. (2017), it extends the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) framework and, since then, it has been expanded to include numerous additional features and functionalities. Its main strength lies in its ability to simultaneously optimize the capacity expansion, energy generation, and dispatch of the system for all the main energy sectors, which leads to an endogenous optimization of the entire energy system. This then also considers the additional electricity demand from sector coupling by considering interactions between all energy sectors, as well as storage, grid, and other flexibility requirements.

GENeSYS-MOD did not require modifications to its core mathematical modeling or solving algorithms for African studies. Instead, the main changes focused on extending the technological scope through enhancements in the data workflow. The model's input datasets were updated to improve clarity, with better documentation explaining variable names, units, and their relations to the nomenclature. Additionally, the linkage script for converting GENeSYS-MOD results into IAMC format was refined to ensure all data could be converted at the same level of detail available within the model. This allowed for better integration with other models in the project and facilitated data exchange.

3.1.1 Model extensions as identified in D3.1

Task	Linux installation guide
Type	IT Related
Specification	The tutorial for installation is focused on installing Windows. It should be extended with at least a Linux section.
Implementation	A PDF file was provided, that explains step-by step how the model can be installed on Linux. Multiple common errors and their solution are mentioned. Furthermore, contact information in case support is needed was provided. The installation guide is also integrated into the readthedocs for GENeSYS-MOD, allowing easy access.
Value Added	Enables users to easily install Julia on a Linux machine.
Effects on Model use	None

Issues and Learnings	Feedback from partners using the installation guide greatly helped to improve the guide to make it easier for users to apply.
Tested/Verified	Installation was successfully tested by users from TU Berlin and external users.
Status	Finalized

Task	Documentation on input datasets
Type	IT Related
Specification	Excel input datasets: the data format is lacking documentation to deeply understand what each value means. Variable names could be clarified. Each variable should be linked to a variable name in the nomenclature (at least the relation with a variable in the nomenclature); Each value should also be associated with a unit (if not in the excel sheet, then in a documentation file, which should be easily accessible).
Implementation	Two input data guides for GENeSYS-MOD were created: one covering the general input data and another focused on the hourly data. Each guide provides detailed explanations of all parameters. For important or complex parameters, examples are included to help users understand their meaning and how to acquire the necessary data for their specific case studies. To ensure the guides meet user needs, a Google Docs to enable collaboration with African partners was used. They were able to comment directly on the documents, highlighting areas where additional information was needed or where there were challenges in understanding or sourcing the data. These comments were continuously integrated into the guides, resulting in iterative improvements and enhanced clarity.
Value Added	New users can now understand the multitude of parameters much easier and profit from an array of examples provided in the data guides helping users to understand what data is needed and where to find it.
Effects on Model use	None
Issues/Learnings	This was an iterative process as partners were able to comment on the guides. This resulted in the team updating the guide in accordance with the questions from the users, helping to improve the guide continuously over time.
Tested/Verified	Partners have used the guide to prepare the data files in all case studies.
Status	In Progress

Task	Linkage Script
Type	IT Related
Specification	A linkage script to convert GENeSYS-MOD results to the IAMC format exists. Nevertheless, this script should allow us to convert all GENeSYS-MOD data with the same level of detail as available in the model (e.g. the script today carries out first some technology or sectors aggregations, making it difficult to reuse those data). Moreover, the linkage script should also allow to convert all input data in IAMC format, to simplify the workflow involving this and other models.

Implementation	GENeSYS-MOD already includes tested scripts to convert its output into IAMC format. However, a more specific linkage script is needed to transfer data from GENeSYS-MOD directly to openTEPES.
Value Added	Facilitating the semi-automatic integration of GENeSYS-MOD and openTEPES for energy system expansion planning, with a detailed focus on the power system.
Effects on Model use	No effects on the usage of GENeSYS-MOD.
Issues/Learnings	It was not yet possible to test the combined use of GENeSYS-Mod and openTEPES within case Study analyses.
Tested/Verified	Not yet.
Status	Finalized, waiting to be tested in a case study.

3.2 openTEPES

The openTEPES model is a decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and transmission expansion plan of a large-scale electric system at a tactical level¹. Besides this expansion planning function, openTEPES can also be used as a detailed operation planning model. The user pre-defines the expansion candidates, so that the model determines the optimal decisions among those specified by the user as possible. Essentially, any power related technology focused on generation and storage can be considered by this tool, including the conventional generation units (thermal -nuclear, gas, coal-), energy storage of different types (hydro, pumped-hydro, battery, electric vehicle being charged according to different possible types of strategies and having or not Vehicle to Grid (V2G) capability, demand response, alkaline water electrolyser, solar thermal) and variable renewable (onshore and offshore wind power, solar PV, run-of-the-river). Besides, the representation of the hydro system based on volume and water inflow data considers the water stream topology (hydro cascade basins).

For openTEPES, the primary adaptations involved better representation of specific energy demand sectors relevant to the African context, such as electricity demand for cooking, industrial cooling, and agriculture. openTEPES can also represent two additional energy carriers (heat and hydrogen). Demand for cooking and industrial cooling can be represented as a heat demand. Distributed energy resources (DERs) were also integrated more effectively, allowing the model to represent off-grid and mini-grid solutions within the African energy landscape. Additionally, new linkage scripts were developed to convert input datasets from IAMC format and other sources into a format compatible with openTEPES, improving the interoperability of the model.

3.2.1 Model extensions as identified in D3.1

Task	Linux Installation Guide
Type	IT Related
Specification	The tutorial for installation of this tool is focused on installing it on a Windows operating system. The process of installing openTEPES on a Linux environment is straightforward and its only specificity is related to the creation of the console to run the model. Otherwise, no adaptation has been needed.

¹ Tactical planning is concerned with time horizons of 10-20 years

Implementation	openTEPES was installed under Ubuntu and updated in the installation procedure. This installation set was tested using Gurobi as a commercial solver. It was also tested using HiGHS as the recommended open-source solver, and finally using the glpk solver.
Value Added	Increasing the range of software environments where openTEPES can be run to perform analyses.
Effects on Model use	None
Issues/Learnings	Developing all the software in Python/Pyomo has allowed a straightforward installation in Ubuntu
Tested/Verified	All the cases have been tested
Status	Finalized

Task	Processed input datasets
Type	IT Related
Specification	The input datasets to be fed into this tool should be processed, as described in section 3.1, to represent separately the demand associated with specific uses of electricity of relevance in the African context, as well as DERs within minigrids connected to the main grid, and those making off-grid solutions.
Implementation	<p>There is no proper implementation process for this development. This only involves carrying out a representation of the system tailored to the specific uses of electricity or supply solutions to analyse.</p> <p>To assess specifically the supply of electricity for cooking, this electricity demand should be located in a separate, virtual, node directly connected to the node of the electricity grid modelled representing the node/area of the system where this cooking demand is taking place. A separate virtual node defined in this way should be employed to represent the cooking demand in each area/node of the transmission grid.</p> <p>As for the representation of the supply of electricity through off-grid solutions, each of those areas, to be explicitly considered in the analyses, where the electricity supply is off-grid must be represented as a separate network not connected to the main system/grid. openTEPES can be run considering several unconnected systems providing an operation/expansion solution for each of them. The level of detail to be considered in the representation of each of these unconnected grids should depend on the level of detail needed in the analyses to be performed.</p>
Value Added	Computing specific expansion/operation results for each of several areas where the supply or electricity is arranged off-grid, considering specific features and costs for the technologies involved in the supply of electricity in these areas.
Effects on Model use	None. The openTEPES model should be run the same way regardless of the number of separate grids being considered. Only input data should be framed differently, as already described.
Issues/Learnings	So far there is no African case study with minigrids/off-grid systems prepared to be tested with openTEPES.

Tested/Verified	Not yet.
Status	Finalized, waiting to be tested.

Task	Linkage script from IAMC to openTEPES
Type	IT Related
Specification	A linkage script to convert openTEPES results to the IAMC data format already exists. However, an appropriate framework needs to be developed to produce input datasets for openTEPES out of the IAMC datasets produced by GENeSYS-MOD and data from other sources that are also required.
Implementation	Scripts which are used to produce data sets in openTEPES data format out of those in the common project data format already exist. The functioning of these has been tested previously. Then, these should be used to produce data in openTEPES format from those produce by GENeSYS-MOD. Given that these will not comprise all the data to be used as an input by openTEPES, additional data need to be collected and formatted appropriately, according to the openTEPES data format, to produce a complete dataset to be input into openTEPES. The set of additional data to collect and format should vary with the case study considered.
Value Added	Paving the use for the semiautomatic combined use of GENeSYS-MOD and openTEPES in analyses involving the planning of the expansion of an energy system and, considering a higher level of detail, the power system within it.
Effects on Model use	openTEPES should be run the same way it is normally run. Only the way to frame input data should change with respect to other analyses.
Issues/Learnings	We have not been able to test the combined use of GENeSYS-MOD and openTEPES within case Study analyses.
Tested/Verified	Not yet.
Status	Finalized, waiting to be tested.

3.3 plan4res

plan4res is a power system model, which includes capacity expansion (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections of a given year), optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and simulation of the system operation. plan4res focuses on electricity. It includes all power generation technologies, electricity storage technologies, and a (usually aggregated) representation of the interconnections between regions (the transmission grid within one region is not represented, nevertheless, the granularity of regions can be adapted to the modelling needs).

plan4res underwent improvements primarily in the areas of input data pre-processing and linkage scripts. The model was adapted to better handle off-grid demand and rural electrification scenarios, ensuring a more accurate representation of decentralized energy solutions. The installation process, which was previously complex, was significantly streamlined. It was reduced to a three-steps procedure involving cloning the install repository, running the installation script and running the script for configuring the environment. These changes enhanced the model's usability, making it more accessible to a wider range of users.

3.3.1 Model extensions as identified in D3.1

Task	Simplified installation & Guide
Type	IT Related
Specification	Installing plan4res is quite complex and requires following a number of different steps. In a further version, the installation procedure will be simplified and will necessitate only 3 main steps: 1- clone from a GitHub repository 2- run an installation script (which will in one command create the whole platform including download of a sif image containing the whole environment and dependencies, installing the software components –in particular SMS++, and installing the launching and data treatment scripts) and; 3- (optional) run a configuration script (mostly if the software is installed on a server and users are running it on their own sessions)
Implementation	The new installation scripts are available in the new plan4res repo https://github.com/plan4res ; Everything is installed by launching one script which embeds all the (numerous) steps that were necessary before, including updates of configuration files The installation script can handle both individual machine and server (including clusters)
Value Added	Simplifies drastically the install process
Effects on Model use	none
Issues/Learnings	-
Tested/Verified	Yes/Yes
Status	Finalised

Task	Solver dependence
Type	IT Related
Specification	Solvers dependence: SMS++ can be used with different solvers: CPLEX, Gurobi, Scip and Highs. We will include the possibility of choosing the solver in a further release. Note that CPLEX and Gurobi are commercial solvers which may require buying a license.
Implementation	The new version (2.0) includes possibility of choosing among the 4 solvers: CPLEX, Gurobi, SCIP and HiGHS. (for CPLEX and Gurobi, a licence is necessary which needs to be provided by the user). The default version is with HiGHS.
Value Added	Plan4res is now no more dependent on a commercial solver
Effects on Model use	If using HiGHS, solving is much slower.
Issues/Learnings	With SCIP it is still not possible to run the capacity expansion, due to limitations in SCIP. The SCIP team is working on it.
Tested/Verified	Yes/Yes
Status	Finalised

Task	Windows installation
Type	IT Related
Specification	Windows installation. The current solution relies on the use of the virtual machine software Vagrant. We plan to test the use of WSL, which may be more efficient.
Implementation	The standard Linux installation procedure works with WSL. It requires that the user has WSL installed.
Value Added	Allows to skip the use of Vagrant which makes everything extremely slow
Effects on Model use	none
Issues/Learnings	
Tested/Verified	No/No
Status	Ongoing

Task	Linkage Script
Type	IT Related
Specification	Adaptation of the plan4res linkage scripts to the context of openMod4Africa
Implementation	Linkage scripts: 2 linkage scripts were available: one creates plan4res input datasets out of IAMC data from GENeSYS-MOD, and one converts plan4res outputs to the IAMC format. Those scripts have been adapted to the context of the project as well as to some changes in the variables produced by GENeSYS-MOD. A third script which allows to create a IAMC file containing all necessary data directly from GENeSYS-MOD raw outputs has also been implemented, given that some variables were not available in the GENeSYS-MOD linkage scripts
Value Added	Allows to run plan4res based on outputs of GENeSYS-MOD and to visualise plan4res outputs in the OM4A visualisation tool
Effects on Model use	none
Issues/Learnings	-
Tested/Verified	Yes/Yes
Status	Finalised

Task	Installation on AWS cluster
Type	IT Related
Specification	Make available an AWS cluster with plan4res installation, so that case study teams can run plan4res on this cluster
Implementation	An AWS cluster has been made available. The standard Linux installation procedure is working on this cluster: plan4res has been installed on this cluster. Configuration scripts are available in the plan4res GitHub to allow external users to run plan4res on this cluster (which requires getting credentials, only available to project partners)
Value Added	Make possible for users with no access to powerful enough IT to run plan4res on a parallel cluster, if necessary in the case studies
Effects on Model use	none

Issues/Learnings	-
Tested/Verified	Yes/Yes
Status	Finalised

Task	Update documentation
Type	IT Related
Specification	A documentation for installing and running plan4res is available but it requires updates linked to: - the simplification conducted on the installation - the new use case on AWS - some more advanced scripts for launching the different models which have been implemented in the last months
Implementation	The documentation has been updated and is now complete. It includes an installation tutorial (both for Linux / windows, including uses on clusters) and a tutorial how to run the model, as well as a full description of input/output data and their formats.
Value Added	New users can now understand the model, its large set of inputs and outputs, create some datasets, install and run the model
Effects on Model use	none
Issues/Learnings	-
Tested/Verified	Yes/Yes
Status	Finalised

3.4 InfraFair

The InfraFair model determines the network utilisation by agents (demand and generators using the network) and countries. Based on this utilisation and assuming that it reflects the economic benefits received by agents, it determines the responsibility of each agent in the construction of each element in the network. In order to reasonably reflect the stakeholder's utilisation of network infrastructure, multiple representative snapshots of the annual network usage should be provided. InfraFair is a decision support tool for network cost allocation and tariff design for regional power transmission infrastructure, but it can be used for national infrastructure as well as other types of infrastructures operating on the same principle of flow (e.g. gas and hydrogen). Hence, the model considers all assets that have a flow usage such as power lines, transformers, breaks, series capacitors and phase shifting transformers.

InfraFair did not require fundamental adaptations, as it had already been developed with an African energy context in mind. However, improvements were made to the latest version of the model to extend its capabilities in energy loss allocation. The updated version allows for more precise tracking of power injections, withdrawals, and losses across network assets. This enhancement ensures that energy losses can be accurately allocated to national systems or individual network users, improving the granularity of energy flow analysis.

3.4.1 Model extensions as identified in D3.1

Task	Installation on Linux (& Mac)
Type	IT Related

Specification	Test the installation of the model on Linux and Mac as well.
Implementation	InfraFair has been installed and tested on Linux (Ubuntu) and Mac using the Mac Pro machine, with the same instructions (except where the syntax is different, e.g., pip3 instead of pip) used for Windows. Thus, there has been no need to provide additional Linux or Mac-specific instructions, but just hints added to the documentation on the syntax differences. Internally, the use of the path was different from one Operating System (OS) to the other. Particularly, the use of back-slash and forward-slash was different across the OSs. The model has been improved to detect the OS and adapt the default use of this special character accordingly.
Value Added	Increasing the range of software environments where InfraFair can be run to perform analyses.
Effects on Model use	None.
Issues/Learnings	Developing all the software in Python allowed a straightforward installation on different operating systems with careful consideration of back- and forward- slashes when using them in default settings (static variables).
Tested/Verified	The correct functioning of the model for the standard examples provided has been tested and verified.
Status	Finalized.

Task	Installation Guide
Type	IT Related change
Specification	The full documentation of the model is provided online on: https://infrafair.readthedocs.io/en/latest/ . However, an offline consolidated installation manual (PDF) that contains all the documentation and installation instructions for different operating systems would be beneficial for easy dissemination.
Implementation	All the documentation has been put together, adding the different version releases of the model as well as guidance for installing and running it on different operating systems.
Value Added	Providing a handy single source of guidance that could be viewed offline.
Effects on Model use	None.
Issues/Learnings	A group of users prefer offline materials and find them more accessible than online sources. This is particularly relevant for African users in locations where the internet is not always available.
Tested/Verified	Verified
Status	In the process of being finalized

Task	Upgrading Python Compatibility
Type	Model related change
Specification	Owing to the dependencies the model is subject to, the tool currently requires a specific version of Python (3.8) and is not compatible with recent versions. During

	the training workshop, partners requested to upgrade the Python version to allow it to run on the latest version of Python.
Implementation	The issue of the dependencies has been resolved by replacing depreciated functions, which are not compatible with newer versions of Python, with other functions that are compatible with higher (later) versions of Python. The entire software package is now available for any version of Python higher than 3.8. If a lower (earlier) version of Python needs to be used, the model can still run on it without a problem, but this would require installing it manually and not with the pip install command.
Value Added	The model can now run on different Python environments and running it would not necessarily require the user to create a dedicated environment (although it is still recommended).
Effects on Model use	None. The model usage and installation remain the same. Only the internal choice of functions from another library has been changed.
Issues/Learnings	It is always good to track the dependencies and check if some functions have been or are expected to be depreciated and replace them with alternative functions to keep the model healthy to run on newer Python versions.
Tested/Verified	Tested and verified.
Status	Finalized

3.4.2 Additional model extensions for InfraFair

Task	New version on Scenario Explorer
Type	IT Related change
Specification	Register the new version of InfraFair in the Scenario Explorer in order for this to be used within the project case studies already including the losses allocation functionality.
Implementation	The request for registration of the new model version has been filled with the IIASA team and the model input data and output can be exchanged with the Scenario explorer.
Value Added	Registering the new model allows users to benefit from its new functionalities and to use it on different OSs with the default settings.
Effects on Model use	None.
Issues/Learnings	When no major changes are introduced, particularly to the data input and output format related to regions, the model registration is easy, and only the version number needs to be updated.
Tested/Verified	Tested and verified.
Status	Finalized.

Task	Linkage scripts from and to IAMC
Type	IT Related change
Specification	A linkage script to convert InfraFair results to the IAMC data format already exists. However, an appropriate framework needs to be considered to produce input

	datasets for InfraFair out of the IAMC datasets produced by GENeSYS-MOD, OpenTEPES and Plan4RES. An appropriate framework to produce input datasets for InfraFair out of the IAMC datasets produced by GENeSYS-MOD, OpenTEPES and Plan4RES.
Implementation	Scripts which are used to produce data sets in InfraFair data format out of those in the common project data format already exist. This was implemented and tested previously for case studies with OpenTEPES. Then, these should be used to produce data in InfraFair format from that produced by GENeSYS-MOD and Plan4RES. Given that these may not comprise all the data to be used as an input by InfraFair, additional data might need to be collected and formatted appropriately, according to the InfraFair data format, to produce a complete dataset to be input into InfraFair. The set of additional data to collect and format should vary with the case study considered.
Value Added	Paving the use for the semiautomatic combined use of GENeSYS-MOD, or plan4res, and InfraFair in analyses involving the planning of the expansion of an energy system and allocation of the cost of the electricity grid for the power system within it.
Effects on Model use	InfraFair should be run the same way it is normally run. Only the way to frame input data should change with respect to other analyses.
Issues/Learnings	We have not been able to test the combined use of GENeSYS-MOD, or openTEPES, and InfraFair within case Study analyses.
Tested/Verified	Not yet.
Status	Finalized, waiting to be tested

3.5 OnSSET

OnSSET is a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas. The OnSSET code base is modular and allows the users to specify spatial and temporal resolution of the analysis, GIS input data, technologies and costs. OnSSET is a bottom-up medium- to long-term optimization model that attempts to determine the least-expensive supply option to achieve universal electrification in each site by combining population settlements with various geographical features, socioeconomic data, and demographic information.

OnSSET allows users to simulate different electrification pathways—ranging from centralized grid expansion to decentralized off-grid and mini-grid solutions—OnSSET provides actionable insights into how investment, technology choices, and policy priorities can impact long-term energy access outcomes. This makes it especially useful to align electrification strategies with national development goals and international commitments.

OnSSET was already designed for African energy modeling and did not require modifications to accommodate the project’s case studies. The model is a key tool for rural electrification planning, supporting the representation of off-grid energy solutions. However, refinements were made to ensure better compatibility with other models in the project, particularly in data preprocessing and integration of workflows.

These refinements included suggestions to spatial data harmonization, improved interoperability with complementary GIS software, workflows to generate data visualizations and summarize the scenarios in tables and maps.

3.5.1 Model extensions as identified in D3.1

Task	Installation guide
Type	IT Related
Specification	Provide documentation and videos to support the process of installing OnSSET on different platform, along with information on how to solve common issues and shortcuts to avoid complex operations.
Implementation	Installation guide and videos are ready. Additional tools for ArcGIS were developed as Jupiter Notebooks and could be made available to ArcGIS Pro users.
Value Added	Easier installation for users.
Effects on Model use	-
Issues/Learnings	-
Tested/Verified	Tested
Status	Finalized

Task	Data collection
Type	IT Related
Specification	The input data for OnSSET can be collected by using different open data sources that implemented OnSSET in different context. Collect sample data and indicate how to find or create new datasets for OnSSET.
Implementation	Data tested with different implementations of OnSSET and in particular the Global Electrification Platform.
Value Added	The installation guide already suggest which data are already available to run OnSSET and shows how to prepare the main spatial data that OnSSET requires. The next seminar will provide examples and a new document is in preparation to specifically address the data preparation task.
Effects on Model use	-
Issues/Learnings	-
Tested/Verified	Tested
Status	Finalized

Task	Linkage script
Type	IT Related
Specification	Development of script to load the output of OnSSET on the IAMC format.
Implementation	The scripts were developed by focusing on a summarized version of the OnSSET output. OnSSET generates several Gigabyte of output as csv files, and the scripts read the output to create an Excel file with the information at a country level. The linkage scripts were posted on GitHub and some modifications were requested.

	The input for OnSSET are spatial data that cannot be loaded by using a web interface.
Value Added	Data now available in IAMC format.
Effects on Model use	-
Issues/Learnings	-
Tested/Verified	Tested
Status	Finalized

3.6 EV-PV

EV-PV is designed to support decision-making and strategic planning for electric mobility in a given region of interest. It was originally developed as a set of geospatial data layers and “calculation modules” within the Citiwatts GIS tool (<https://citiwatts.eu/>) developed for Europe. At that stage, the model was focused only on privately-owned cars and relied on European mobility patterns and datasets.

To adapt EV-PV for Africa’s unique context, it has undergone significant adaptations and enhancements. Key modifications include:

- Supporting multiple vehicle types (cars, motorbikes, etc.) and a wider range of charging options.
- Performing endogenous simulation of mobility demand (including intra-urban travel patterns that were previously excluded) using entirely open-source, globally accessible datasets.
- Enabling scenario-based analyses to explore diverse EV adoption and infrastructure deployment futures.
- Upgrading PV production models to include more installation configurations and technologies.
- Incorporating ex-post modules for CO₂-emission reduction estimates and cost-benefit analyses.
- Providing comprehensive end-user documentation and worked examples.

As a result of these efforts, EV-PV has been transformed into a standalone Python package, installable and usable in the same way as the other models developed in the project, ensuring a coherent ecosystem of tools. It now comes as a fully integrated, end-to-end framework, covering the entire workflow from data pre-processing to EV-PV complementarity assessment, and providing all the key inputs and outputs needed for transport electrification studies in Africa.

A partial integration of this standalone tool into the new African GIS platform (currently still under development) is also planned for the project’s final year, providing an alternative visual interface for users. However, this integration will require further development of the GIS platform to support the new functionalities introduced by the enhanced model.

Finally, insights from the scientific literature and case study partners have highlighted the importance of extending the model to include public transport, which accounts for a significant share of passenger mobility in many regions. This was entirely outside the scope of the original EV-PV model. After evaluating several options, a completely new model was developed from scratch to specifically address this topic. This new model is also delivered as a standalone Python tool and is progressively documented:

<https://github.com/jeremydumoulin/gtfs4ev> .

3.6.1 Model extension as identified in D3.1

Task	Multiple vehicle types and charging powers
Type	Model related change
Specification	Extending the technological scope of the model to a broader range of EV types (e.g., cars, motorbikes, plug-in hybrids, ...) and charging powers.
Implementation	Users can now define a fleet composed of various vehicle types, each with specific attributes (battery capacity, energy consumption, and maximum tolerated charging power). The model also supports a range of charging station power levels and their relative availability at different charging locations.
Value Added	This enhancement enables more realistic simulation with flexible simulations technological granularity. It is particularly useful for conducting "what-if" analyses in regions where the evolution of EV adoption and charging infrastructure remains uncertain.
Effects on Model use	The user must now define a list of EVs and the available charging power options, specifying the properties associated with each.
Issues/Learnings	Data is often unavailable in African contexts, requiring reliance on proxy datasets from other regions.
Tested/Verified	Successfully applied in a case study for Addis Ababa. Further applications are in progress with East African partners in OpenMod4Africa in other cities.
Status	Finalized

Task	Mobility demand simulation
Type	Model related change
Specification	Performing endogenous simulation of mobility demand (including intra-urban travel patterns that were previously excluded)
Implementation	We have implemented a so-called spatial interaction model that estimates commuting transport demand by modelling vehicle flows between origins (homes) and destinations (workplaces) using a gravity model. This model is a state-of-the-art and calibration-free (no data required) model, and users can also incorporate additional weekday travel demand (e.g., shopping or leisure) by adding extra kilometres travelled.
Value Added	Allows for simulating commuting flows even if no data is available, providing the origin and destination of every EV, using only data available on OpenStreetMap (https://www.openstreetmap.org/).
Effects on Model use	This approach requires dividing the region of interest into sub-zones, which slightly limits spatial resolution. Additionally, it relies on routing with OpenRouteService (https://openrouteservice.org/ - need an API key), which slightly increases the computation time.
Issues/Learnings	Routing is sometimes not working in African contexts. A fallback mechanism was added to estimate road distances when routing fails.
Tested/Verified	Successfully applied in a case study for Addis Ababa. Further applications are in progress with East African partners in OpenMod4Africa in other cities.
Status	Finalized

Task	PV Production
Type	Model related change
Specification	Upgrading PV production models to include more installation configurations and technologies.
Implementation	Leveraging the open-source PVLib library by Anderson et al. (2023) (widely adopted in the photovoltaics research and engineering community) the model now supports various installation types (rooftop, ground-mounted, and systems with or without solar tracking). Users can also fine-tune simulations by specifying panel characteristics and system losses.
Value Added	This allows for more comprehensive PV scenarios and introduces temperature effects into PV production estimation, which were previously not considered explicitly.
Effects on Model use	Users are now required to specify the type of PV installation.
Issues/Learnings	PVLib depends on weather data. Here, we use data from PVGIS, which may occasionally fail for very low latitude regions. The code includes a fallback mechanism to handle these cases.
Tested/Verified	Successfully applied in a case study for Addis Ababa. Further applications are in progress with WP6 partners in other cities.
Status	Finalized

Task	Economic and environmental assessment
Type	Model related change
Specification	Incorporating ex-post modules for CO ₂ -emission reduction estimates and cost-benefit analyses.
Implementation	A dedicated Python script has been developed to process EV-PV model outputs and simulate both aggregated and per-vehicle CO ₂ emission reductions. It also includes calculations of economic savings from reduced fuel consumption.
Value Added	Enables an assessment of environmental and economic benefits.
Effects on Model use	None.
Issues/Learnings	Required the model outputs to be structured in a format that is easily post-processed.
Tested/Verified	Planned to be use by East African partners in OpenMod4Africa
Status	Finalized

Task	Documentation
Type	IT Related
Specification	Providing comprehensive end-user documentation and worked examples
Implementation	Complete documentation is now available on readthedocs, covering installation, usage, and methodology of the model. In parallel, the full source code has been

	published under a dedicated GitHub organization to ensure a well-structured project.
Value Added	Provides clear, accessible guidance for users of all levels, improving usability and adoption.
Effects on Model use	None.
Issues/Learnings	This is an iterative process. While version 1 is complete, improvements will be made based on model evolution and user feedback.
Tested/Verified	WP6 partners were able to install the model following the guidance of the documentation.
Status	Finalized (but subject to continuous improvement)

3.6.2 Additional model extensions for EV-PV

Task	Simulate public transport modes (buses, minibuses, ...)
Type	Model related change
Specification	Further develop the EV-PV model to accommodate both formal (e.g., regular buses, Bus Rapid Transit) and informal (e.g., minibuses) public transport modes.
Implementation	To integrate these new mobility modes, an entirely new model has been developed using a novel methodology. It relies on GTFS (General Transit Feed Specification) data, which is widely available and captures both formal and informal public transport in many African cities.
Value Added	Public transport represents the majority of urban mobility in many African cities. This model enables the inclusion of this essential segment, broadening the scope of the mobility models available in the toolbox.
Effects on Model use	A new model must be installed. However, its installation and usage follow a logic that is very similar to the EV-PV model, ensuring ease of integration for current users.
Issues/Learnings	GTFS data often requires significant pre-processing and augmentation to accurately reflect real-world transport operations. Additional features were implemented to allow users to adjust the data (for example, by inserting idle times at stops or terminal points) to better represent actual public transport schedules.
Tested/Verified	A preliminary comparative study between multiple cities has been conducted. The model is currently being applied in a case study for Addis Ababa and is planned for use in WP5 case studies focusing on the electrification of BRT and bus systems in Dakar.
Status	Finalized (awaits comprehensive documentation and additional use cases)

4 Conclusion

The activities carried out under Task 3.3 ‘Development of the extensions of the open-source models’ have successfully led to the implementation of the model extensions identified in previous stages of the project. These updates ensure that the models included in the OM4A Toolbox are well-suited for analysing the complex and diverse energy transition pathways across the African continent.

For all models, we significantly improved documentation, enabled compatibility with additional environments (e.g., Linux), and improved and tested the linkages for combined model use.

The models GENeSYS-MOD, openTEPES, and plan4res have undergone targeted extensions related to their technological scope, particularly on the demand side and off-grid network representation. These improvements were achieved through adaptations in the data workflow, avoiding the need for changes to their core mathematical formulations or solving algorithms. These enhancements now enable the models to more accurately capture specific African energy system characteristics, such as the representation of cooking demand and decentralized electricity access.

InfraFair and OnSSET, already developed with the African context in mind, did not require modifications. Their integration into the Toolbox was mainly focused on usability and linkage improvements and the development of documentation to ensure effective deployment in the case studies.

The EV-PV model was extended to include a wider range of transport modes, reflecting the diversity of urban and rural mobility needs across Africa. In parallel, the PV potential estimation methodology was adapted to better reflect local geospatial and infrastructure conditions.

In addition to model development, a strong emphasis was placed on accessibility and usability. All the models have been documented and made available through a centralized online repository (<https://africanenergymodels.net>), with clear guidance for installation, operation, and linkage. Training materials have also been developed and shared (<https://github.com/OM4A-Training-Material/>.github) to empower the African stakeholders to independently apply the Toolbox in their own regional and national planning exercises.

5 References

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